

Assessing the Use and Effectiveness of Automation on University Library Services in Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18094170>

Abstract

Purpose: The study examined the use and impact of automation on library services in university libraries in Abuja, using the University of Abuja and the African University of Science and Technology as case studies. The objectives were to identify which library services had been automated, assess the extent to which automation had improved these services, determine the impact of automation on library usage, identify the challenges faced by libraries in automating their operations, and suggest ways to enhance the automation of library services.

Methodology: The study employed a survey research design, using simple random and purposive sampling techniques to select 150 respondents, forming the sample size. Data collection involved questionnaires and interviews, with data analysed through frequency tables, percentages, means, and standard deviations.

Findings: The study found that the university libraries had not yet achieved full automation. It also found that automation had a positive impact on the usage of library services by patrons and led to improvements in various aspects of these services. Despite this, the libraries had not fully adopted automation due to challenges such as a lack of technological support from the parent institutions, inadequate power supply, and the poor attitude of some library staff.

Conclusion: The study also proposed that subscribing to online databases and using library management software could help improve library services.

Keywords: Library Automation; Library services in Nigeria; Nigerian University Libraries

Introduction

As universities in Nigeria strive to meet the demands of a digital age, automation has emerged as both a catalyst and a challenge for library service delivery—reshaping access to knowledge, redefining the librarian's role, and testing the resilience of traditional systems. The inadequacies of traditional librarianship in the face of rising technological demands, current realities, and the need to improve library services have become increasingly evident (Irenea et al., 2018). Outdated workflows, limited collaboration, and shallow expertise must be addressed to curb the ineffective service paradigm that is rampant in many Nigerian libraries. In Nigerian university libraries, automation has become a pivotal strategy for improving efficiency, expanding access to resources, and redefining the scope of library services. Automation involves implementing various Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) to carry out tasks that traditionally required manual effort. Specifically, library automation refers

to the deployment and integration of computers and other ICT tools to enhance the delivery of relevant information to users promptly, thereby supporting and optimising a wide range of library activities. These activities include acquisitions, cataloguing, circulation, serial management, and the provision of diverse reference services, all aimed at improving efficiency and accessibility within the library system (Oladokun & Kolawole, 2019).

Information and communication technology (ICT) and the internet have recently brought about a significant transformation in libraries, transitioning them from traditional, manual operations to more modern, technology-driven concepts. According to Oluwole et al. (2019), automation in academic libraries involves not only restructuring existing functions but also reinventing and innovating services to meet contemporary needs. Similarly, Omosor (2014) and Janakiraman et al. (2015) emphasized the crucial role that technology now plays in academic libraries, highlighting how it greatly enhances staff performance and leads to improvements in the efficiency, accuracy, and overall quality of various tasks. Moreover, Yalagi and Mane (2021) observed that the Library Automation System is becoming increasingly vital as the number of users continues to grow, helping to facilitate a seamless circulation process that supports an efficient and effective system within the library's circulation section, ultimately enhancing user experience and operational productivity.

The library is a comprehensive resource center that consolidates materials in various formats, meticulously organized by experienced library and information professionals or subject matter experts. Its primary goal is to educate, inform, and entertain a wide range of audiences, thereby fostering individual learning as well as contributing to broader societal development. Over time, the library has evolved from relying solely on traditional, manual methods to adopting automated services in order to keep pace with the changing roles and technological advancements. This study focuses on examining how this shift towards automation has influenced the delivery and quality of library services specifically within university libraries located in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Nigeria. The specific objectives of the research include identifying which library services have been automated at the University of Abuja and the African University of Science and Technology, analyzing the improvements and efficiencies gained from automation, assessing the impact of automation on library patronage and usage patterns, exploring the challenges and obstacles encountered during the automation process, and proposing actionable strategies to enhance and optimize automation efforts at these academic institutions.

Statement of Problem

Despite the global shift toward digital transformation in higher education, many Nigerian university libraries continue to grapple with limited adoption and uneven implementation of automation technologies, as evidenced in many failed automation attempts. While automation has great potential to enhance efficiency, improve access to resources, and streamline service delivery, its integration in Nigerian university libraries has been hindered by bottlenecks such as widespread funding

inadequacies, comatose infrastructure, a shortage of technical expertise, and inconsistent policy support. This reality means that library operations remain heavily manual, with delays experienced in information retrieval, unsatisfied users, and high inefficiencies in resource management.

Furthermore, questions remain about the effectiveness, sustainability, and actual impact of automation systems introduced. There is limited empirical evidence to determine whether automation has truly transformed library services in Nigerian universities or if its adoption is still superficial and fragmented. This lack of knowledge makes it hard for stakeholders—policy makers, university administrators, and librarians—to make well-informed decisions about future investments in library automation.

Therefore, a systemic assessment of the use and effectiveness of automation in Nigerian university libraries remains of high importance to determine the current state, evaluate the current impact on service delivery, and identify the barriers and opportunities for improvement.

Research Questions

1. Which library services have been automated at the University of Abuja and the libraries of the African University of Science and Technology?
2. To what extent have services in university libraries improved due to automation?
3. To what extent has the automation of library services affected how students and staff use the services at university libraries?
4. What challenges do university libraries face in automating their services?
5. In what ways can the automation of library operations at the University of Abuja and the African University of Science and Technology libraries be improved?

Literature review

Libraries and librarians recognise the vital role that technology and its applications play in fulfilling patrons' information needs in the 21st century. The introduction of automation in Nigerian university libraries has been driven by the aim of improving service quality, increasing operational efficiency, and meeting the rising demand for digital access to information (Odigie, 2022). Otunla (2016); Chiemeke (2004); and Ukachi, Nwachukwu, and Onuoha (2014) indicated that the automation of library services involves using computers to support manual tasks, such as data management and managing complex activities, to ensure efficiency and effectiveness at a low cost. Similarly, Olayinka and Buraimo (2021) observed that the adoption of automation technologies in Nigerian university libraries has grown over the past decade, leading to improved service quality, better information retrieval, and easier resource sharing. This progress has also elevated staff skills and made library processes more efficient.

In this context, previous research conducted by Kari and Baro in 2014 revealed that university libraries across Nigeria frequently utilise a variety of library management software, including KOHA, SLAM,

and VIRTUA, to improve and streamline their library operations. Furthermore, Akintoye in 2022 discussed the automation of library functions through the use of RFID technology and barcodes, emphasising that the adoption of information and communication technologies (ICTs) significantly reduces the time required for both end users and library staff. This technological integration not only prevents the duplication of work but also ensures that library services operate more smoothly and efficiently. Additionally, automated cataloguing and circulation processes have contributed to a reduction in manual labour, allowing library staff to devote more time and resources to more complex and value-added tasks, such as providing user support and delivering information literacy training, as outlined by Ayodele and Akintwale (2022).

Library automation plays a crucial role in transforming modern library management by enhancing efficiency and service quality. It streamlines essential activities such as cataloguing, inventory management, and maintenance, ensuring that resources are accessible and well-organised. By networking for resource sharing, automation maximises the utility of collections while providing users with seamless access to a vast array of information sources via the internet. These systems enable libraries to effectively collect and analyse data on usage, collection performance, and user preferences, empowering them to make smarter, data-driven decisions. Furthermore, automation not only safeguards knowledge through organised preservation but also ensures consistent operations by integrating all subsystems into a centralised database. Embracing such technologies is crucial for libraries seeking to remain relevant, efficient, and responsive in today's information-driven world.

Similarly, Ejiroghene (2020), Duru (2023), and Omoju (2023) discussed several challenges faced in automating libraries in Nigeria. These include inadequate funding, which restricts the procurement of essential hardware, software, and reliable power sources. Additionally, there are issues related to poor maintenance and update culture, as well as inconsistent power supply and inadequate internet infrastructure in some regions. Furthermore, there is a significant shortage of trained personnel capable of managing and effectively utilising automated systems, which hinders the successful automation of Nigerian libraries.

Additionally, Muhammad (2022) assessed that the library scene has changed significantly in terms of collection, organisation, and services in the age of ICTs. Users' expectations and attitudes have shifted in various ways. Consequently, users' information-seeking behaviour has evolved. Looking ahead, the future of automation in Nigerian university libraries depends on integrating advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, and big data analytics. These technologies can further improve resource management, user experience, and decision-making processes in library operations (Odigie, 2022). The idea of library automation emerged from the need for current materials without limitations. Library automation has become essential for efficiently managing all library operations and services, enabling the delivery of excellent service.

Research methodology

This study used a descriptive survey research design. As of 2025, there are seven universities in FCT, comprising six private and one federal university (National Universities Commission (NUC), 2025). The population for the study includes students, faculty members, and librarians from one federal and one private university—specifically, 35 librarians, 115 faculty/academic staff, and 300 students, totalling 450 individuals. Simple random and purposive sampling techniques were employed to select 150 respondents from the total population to minimise bias.

The universities selected are listed in Table 1. The research tool used in this study was a self-designed structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into two parts. Part A included demographic details about librarians and library users. Part B asked respondents to answer questions created by the researcher regarding the use and impact of automation on library services in university libraries. In line with the research questions, respondents rated each statement based on their level of agreement using a four-point Likert scale (1932): Strongly Agree (SA) (4 points), Agree (A) (3 points), Disagree (D) (2 points), and Strongly Disagree (SD) (1 point).

Results and Discussion of Findings

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	No. of Respondents (N=150)	Percentage (%)
Male	65	43
Female	85	57
Total	150	100

Source: Field survey 2023

Table 1 shows that 65 respondents were male, representing 43%, while 85 respondents were female, representing 57%. This indicates that female respondents made up the majority of the sample.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Age

Age	No. of Respondents (N=150)	Percentage (%)
Less than 20	25	16.5
20-29	45	30
30-39	25	16.5
40-49	30	20
50-59	15	10
60-70	10	7

Total	150	100
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Source: Field survey 2023

Table 3: Work Experience

Working Experience	No. of Respondents (N=35)	Percentage (%)
1-10	15	43
11-20	9	26
21-30	6	17
31-40	5	14
Total	35	100

Source: Field survey 2023

Table 3 shows that the majority of respondents have between 1 and 10 years of working experience, accounting for 43% in both institutions under study, confirming that most respondents were young.

Research Question One

Table 4: Which library services have been automated at the University libraries?

S/N	Services	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	Internet service	45	35	50	20	2.70	Agree
2	Bibliography	30	30	40	50	2.26	Disagree
3	User education/Information literacy	35	25	55	35	2.40	Disagree
4	Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI)	20	15	50	65	1.93	Disagree
5	Interlibrary loan	25	30	40	55	2.16	Disagree
6	Circulation/lending	35	30	40	45	2.36	Disagree
7	Abstracting and indexing	30	25	45	45	2.20	Disagree
8	Cataloguing and classification	20	30	50	50	2.13	Disagree
9	Current awareness	30	25	45	50	2.23	Disagree
10	Reference	25	25	50	50	2.16	Disagree
11	Referral	20	25	50	55	2.06	Disagree
Sectional mean		2.24				Disagree	

Source: Field survey 2023

Table 4 indicates that the majority of library services at the university libraries have not yet been automated. However, the findings also show that internet services are available.

Research Question Two

Table 5: To what extent have services in University libraries improved as a result of automation?

S/N	Effect of Automation	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	Library automation enhances user satisfaction of library services	50	40	35	25	2.70	Agree
2	Library automation enhances multiple access to library information	45	45	30	30	2.70	Agree
3	Library automation leads to easy access to library information	55	40	20	35	2.70	Agree
4	Library automation saves time of library users in search for information	60	40	35	15	2.97	Agree
5	Library automation leads to increased performance of library staff	50	40	30	30	2.73	Agree
6	Through Library automation, materials/resources needed for teaching, learning, and research become easy to access	70	40	20	20	3.06	Agree
7	Library automation boosts the image of the Institution and the web metric ranking	75	35	25	15	2.63	Agree
8	The use of ICTs in the library increases the efficiency of service delivery	65	50	30	5	3.16	Agree
Sectional mean						2.83	Agree

Source: Field survey 2023

The data presented in Table 5 indicates that, although the majority of respondents believe that the libraries at the University of Abuja and the African University of Science and Technology have not yet fully automated their services, they remain optimistic that the implementation of automation will ultimately lead to significant improvements in the quality and efficiency of the library's services.

Research Question Three

Table 6: To what extent has the automation of library services influenced the use of the services at the University of Abuja and African University of Science and Technology libraries?

S/N	Automation Practices	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	Use of library management software	30	35	50	35	2.40	Disagree
2	Provision of internet facilities	50	40	30	30	2.73	Agree

3	Use of Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC)	25	35	45	50	2.30	Disagree
4	Database Management	25	30	45	50	2.20	Disagree
5	Implementation of library automated systems	50	40	30	30	2.73	Agree
6	Subscription to online databases e.g. (Pro Quest, EBSCO and PubMed).	50	60	25	15	2.96	Agree
7	Ensuring online visibility and access to the library operations	40	60	25	25	2.76	Agree
Sectional mean						2.58	Agree

Source: Field survey 2023

Table 6 shows the extent to which automation of library services has influenced the use of services at the University of Abuja and the African University of Science and Technology. The results revealed that the provision of internet facilities, implementation of library automated systems, subscription to online databases, and ensuring online visibility and access to library operations were generally agreed to have a positive influence on the use of library services, with means of 2.73, 2.73, 2.96, and 2.76, respectively.

Research Question Four

Figure 1: What are the challenges faced by the University of Abuja and African University of Science and Technology libraries in automating their services?

Source: Field survey 2023

The infographic shows the challenges faced by the University of Abuja and the African University of Science and Technology libraries in automating their services. The study identified clear, high-scoring challenges. The primary obstacle is not a lack of user knowledge, but rather a significant lack of institutional support, poor staff attitudes, and infrastructural deficits.

Research Question Five

Table 8: How can automation of library operations at the University of Abuja and the African University of Science and Technology libraries be improved?

S/N	Automation	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	Use of library management software	60	40	25	25	2.90	Agree
2	Provision of internet facilities	65	35	30	20	2.97	Agree
3	Use of the online public access catalogue	55	50	25	20	2.93	Agree
4	Database management	60	50	20	20	3.00	Agree
5	The use of the digital reference service	70	40	30	10	3.13	Agree
6	Implementation of the library automated system	65	55	15	15	3.13	Agree
7	Subscription to an online database	70	50	20	10	3.20	Agree
8	Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI)	60	40	25	25	2.90	Agree
9	Ensure online visibility and access to library operations	70	40	20	20	3.07	Agree
Sectional mean						2.68	Agree

Source: Field survey 2023

The sectional mean of 2.68 supports the conclusion of agreement among the respondents, indicating that libraries should adopt the strategies listed above to improve their operations.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion is based on the study's findings. It revealed that although internet service is available, the University libraries have not yet automated their services. This finding contradicts Otunla's (2016) assertion that university libraries are automated but aligns with Emasealu's (2019) claim that academic libraries still need to achieve full automation.

An interview with respondents from the University of Abuja library revealed that, although the KOHA library management software was available, it had not yet been implemented for use.

The study also observed that respondents believed that the automation of university libraries would improve the library's services by increasing user satisfaction, providing multiple access points for library information, enabling easy access to library information, and saving time when searching for information. This aligns with the study by Anas, Iqbal, and Ahmed (2014), which states that automation has led to improvements in library services.

Furthermore, the study also shows that providing internet facilities, implementing automated library systems, subscribing to online databases, and ensuring online visibility and access to library services were generally agreed to positively influence library use. This supports Akintunde's (2021) findings that the application of automation technologies in Nigerian university libraries has enhanced the use of library services.

The study revealed that the biggest challenges faced by university libraries in automating their services were a lack of technological support from the parent institution, a poor attitude of library staff, and an inadequate power supply. This supports the findings of Ajani and Buraimo (2021) that poor attitudes among library staff are a significant challenge for library automation. The study shows a divergence from that of Dwivedi (1992), who identified failure of suppliers to deliver the necessary equipment, failure of suppliers to provide the required software, and inadequate service response as the challenges facing automation in libraries.

The study also shows that to improve services at university libraries, the following must be in place: use of library management software, provision of internet facilities, use of online public access catalogues, database management, digital reference services, implementation of automated systems, subscriptions to online databases, utilisation of artificial intelligence, and ensuring online visibility and access to library operations. This finding aligns with that of Olagoke and Kolawole (2019) and Anyira (2020), who agree that using library management software and implementing automated systems enhance the library's services.

Suggestions from the respondents interviewed on how the library services can be improved included providing recent technologies such as broadband internet access, artificial intelligence, and library management software, and implementing automated systems.

Conclusion and Recommendation

In conclusion, automating university libraries is essential for delivering effective and efficient services to the institution's faculty, researchers, students, and staff. The quality of library services can be significantly enhanced through the adoption of automation technologies. As centres of learning, university libraries should implement ICT solutions that enable them to meet the informational and educational needs of their users. To provide satisfactory services, full automation of university libraries is necessary.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Prioritise the institutional mandate on automation and funding by establishing a top-down policy at the NUC level that designates library automation as a vital, non-negotiable element of the core ICT infrastructure, ensuring ongoing budgetary allocations for adoption, system upkeep, and maintenance upgrades.
2. Resolve infrastructural bottlenecks in libraries by providing secure and dedicated power supply through solar inverter systems, ensuring consistent power and reducing downtime.
3. Strategic staff upskilling that ensures comprehensive and continuous professional development programs focus on equipping staff with the requisite ICT skills needed to manage and sustain technological programs in libraries.
4. Adopt best practices in phased implementation so that libraries in Nigeria can move beyond the piecemeal efforts common in most libraries today to a phased, integrated strategy that equally accommodates digital services.

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